

RESIDUAL STRENGTH OF GLARE 1 LAMINATES BASED ON J_C TOUGHNESS OF SE(B) SPECIMENS. COMPARISON WITH WIDE SHEET TEST RESULTS.

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ABSTRACT

Fiber-metal laminates (FMLs) are structural composites designed aiming to produce a damage-tolerant and high strength material. Their main characteristic is their very low fatigue crack propagation rates when compared to traditional aeronautical Al alloys. Their application in aeronautical structures demand a deep knowledge of a wide set of mechanical properties and technological values, including both fracture toughness and residual strength. The residual strength of fiber-metal laminates (FMLs) have been traditionally determined by using wide sheet (M(T)) specimens. The use of this geometry requires large quantities of material and heavy laboratorial facilities. On the other hand, a methodology for critical fracture toughness evaluation has been proposed recently, which uses small SE(B) and C(T) specimens with dimensions as suggested by ASTM standards. Fracture toughness (J_c) of GLARE 1 3/2 0.3 laminates was measured employing this methodology on SE(B) specimens with $W = 25.0$ mm. Additionally, residual strength values of M(T) specimens with $W = 150.0$ and 200.0 mm and $2a/W$ ratios of $1/3$ and $1/4$ were experimentally obtained. Based on J_c results from SE(B) specimens the residual strengths of the M(T) specimens were predicted. These values were compared to the experimental ones. Results showed a close agreement between them being the predicted residual strength values slightly lower than the experimental ones and that difference grew as the width did. This fact could be explained as a consequence of a larger stable crack growth at instability presented by the wider M(T) specimens.

KEYWORDS: GLARE, Fiber-Metal Laminates, Residual Strength, Fracture Toughness.

INTRODUCTION

GLARE® laminates are part of the fiber-metal laminates (FMLs) family of structural composite materials. They were created and developed for aeronautical applications at the Technical University of Delft, Netherlands [1-3]. These orthotropic materials were designed aiming to produce damage-tolerant thin sheets with high specific strength to be used in primary structures (fuselage skins) or secondary ones (bulkheads, firewalls, floors, etc.). The main characteristic of GLARE laminates is their very low fatigue crack propagation rates if compared to traditional aeronautical Al alloys. This singular behavior shared by the whole FML family is raised by the fiber-bridging mechanism which restricts the opening of the crack in the loading part of the fatigue cycle, this diminishing the crack growth rates [4, 5]. Although GLARE laminates were basically developed taking advantage of the bridging mechanism, they also present several additional benefits over the monolithic alloys, i.e. high resistance to corrosion, lightning strikes, impact, and flame penetration [6]. GLARE laminates are reinforced by S2 glass fibers and were tailored to overcome some limitations of the former FMLs, aramid-reinforced aluminum laminates (ARALL®). GLARE is being tested for primary structures, mainly for fuselages [4] and will be used as part of the upper fuselage skin in the new Airbus A380 [2, 4]. Commercial GLARE laminates are reinforced by unidirectional fibers, oriented following the loading characteristics of the structure [6]. They are produced with different lay-ups of the type m/n , with m layers of aluminum bonded by n fiber-epoxy prepreg layers ($m = n + 1$). They can be manufactured as thin sheets of dimensions either similar to those of the commercial Al alloys or with

large dimensions, including low complexity shapes and double curvature panels [4, 6]. Figure 1 illustrates a GLARE laminate of lay-up 3/2.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of a GLARE 3/2 laminate.

The application of FMLs to aeronautical structures demands a deep knowledge of a wide set of mechanical properties and other technological values, including their residual strength [7]. In the scope of this work the residual strength is understood as the remaining static strength of the material in presence of a through-the-thickness flaw with fibers cut up to the notch-tip (the crack-bridging mechanism absent). Based on this approach, the use of fracture mechanics concepts and precise fracture toughness values become necessary within residual strength evaluations. Recently, a test methodology based on elastic-plastic fracture mechanics (*J-Integral* and *CTOD* of Schwalbe, δ_3) which uses small C(T) and SE(B) specimens was proposed to evaluate the instability toughness of FMLs. Following this methodology the fracture toughness (J_C , δ_{3C}) is calculated at a critical point corresponding to the occurrence of full or partial instabilities (similar to pop-ins in welded joints) or at the beginning of the maximum load plateau [8, 9].

The objective of the present work was to compare theoretical and experimental residual strength of wide sheet specimens (M(T)) of GLARE 1 3/2 0,3. The theoretical previsions were done based on the fracture toughness (J_C) of small SE(B) specimens measured following the proposed methodology.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Unidirectional commercial GLARE 1 3/2 laminates with S2 glass fibers oriented parallel to the rolling direction of the Al layers (0.3 mm in thickness) were tested. GLARE 1 is made of 7475-T76 alloy and subjected to a permanent stretch after curing for reversing undesirable residual stresses [1]. Some mechanical properties of GLARE 1 3/2 0.3, including Young's modulus parallel (E_1) and perpendicular (E_2) to the fibers and the apparent modulus (E') in the fibers direction, are presented in table 1.

Table 1. Properties of GLARE 1 3/2 0.3 [10].

Post-stretch %	σ_{YS} MPa	σ_U MPa	E_1 GPa	E_2 GPa	E' GPa	Density kg/m ³	Metallic % Vol	Thickness mm
5.0	545	1282	64.0	49.0	51.8	2520	67.9	1.42

Fracture toughness evaluation was performed at room temperature on SE(B) specimens (25.0 mm wide) with notches oriented transversely to the fibers direction and following a proposed methodology developed for FMLs fracture toughness determination [8, 9]. Their main points are:

- Use of standardized C(T) and SE(B) specimens [11]. SE(B) specimens must be used in cases where out of plane crack growth has occurred when using C(T) specimens.

- Notches must be sharp (fibers being cut up to the notch tip). No fatigue precracks are allowed in order to avoid fiber-bridging mechanism.
- Anti-buckling plates must be used to avoid lateral bending.
- Measurement of the load-line displacement for J calculation in C(T) specimens must be made using a clip-gauge in the notch mouth, on the load line. In SE(B) specimens, instead, the machine crosshead displacement is measured and then energy due to indentations must be discounted.
- The anisotropy of the material (orthotropy) is taken into account for J calculation.
- The instabilities in the load vs. load-line displacement records are evaluated in order to establish the occurrence of critical points. When the load drop is higher than 2 % of the current load, the point is considered (conservatively) significant and the critical toughness must be obtained for this point. When the instability does not occur the fracture toughness is measured at the beginning of the maximum load plateau.

Residual strength measurements of M(T) specimens

The residual strength of M(T) specimens of GLARE 1 3/2 0.3 was experimentally measured testing specimens with 150.0 and 200.0 mm width and initial crack to width lengths $2a/W = 1/4$ and $1/3$. Tests were carried out in a 400 kN hydraulic testing machine at room temperature under constant crosshead displacement rate (0.5 mm/min). Anti-buckling plates were necessary to prevent lateral bending of the specimens. The specimens were instrumented by a LVDT for crosshead displacement measurement and load vs. load-line record were obtained. A view of one M(T) specimen ready to be tested is shown in figure 2.

Fig. 2. Experimental evaluation of residual strength of M(T) specimens.

Theoretical residual strength calculations

K_{JC} values were estimated from experimental J_C values by using the following expression [12]:

$$K_{JIC} = \sqrt{J_C E'} \quad (1)$$

where

$$\frac{1}{E'} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{a_{11}a_{22}}{2}\right)} \left[\sqrt{\frac{a_{22}}{a_{11}}} + \frac{2a_{12} + a_{66}}{2a_{11}} \right] \quad (2)$$

The a_{ij} are the compliance matrix components [13], calculated as follows:

$$a_{11} = \frac{1}{E_1}; a_{12} = \frac{-\nu_{12}}{E_1} = \frac{-\nu_{21}}{E_2}; a_{22} = \frac{1}{E_2}; a_{66} = \frac{1}{G_{12}} \quad (3)$$

Equation (2) gives an “apparent” Young’s modulus of the orthotropic material in the considered direction. It applies only if the crack plane coincides with one principal direction [13, 14], as it did throughout this work.

The theoretical residual stresses of M(T) specimens were calculated using the K_I expression taken from the ASTM E561 standard [15], including the crack length correction due to plastic deformation.

$$\sigma_{res} = \frac{K_{JIC}}{\sqrt{\pi a_{eff} \sec \frac{\pi a_{eff}}{W}}} \quad (4)$$

W is the specimen width and a_{eff} is calculated as

$$a_{eff} = a_0 + \frac{1}{2\pi} \left(\frac{K_{JIC}}{\sigma_{YS}} \right)^2 \quad (5)$$

These results were then compared to the experimental ones.

RESULTS

Table 2 shows the fracture toughness values (J_C) obtained from 25.0 mm wide SE(B) specimens and also the estimated values of K_{JIC} of GLARE 1 3/2 0.3.

Table 2. Fracture toughness of GLARE 1 3/2 0.3

J_C kJ/m ²	K_{JIC} MPa.m ^{1/2}
235.22 ± 36.41	110.37

The values of the residual strengths of the M(T) specimens predicted using equation (4) with fracture toughness data of table 2 and the experimental ones are shown in table 3. The last column of the table shows the ratio of experimental to theoretical values.

Table 3. Theoretical and experimental residual strength of M(T) specimens of GLARE 1 3/2 0.3 with notches perpendicular to the fibers.

$2a_0$ mm	W mm	Theoretical MPa	Experimental MPa	Exp./Theor. ratio
37.50	150.00	407.89	425.56	1.043
50.00	150.00	345.41	360.16	1.043
50.00	200.00	359.23	403.11	1.122
66.67	200.00	303.54	344.56	1.135

DISCUSSION

Analyzing both fracture toughness and tensile properties, GLARE 1 soundly possesses the rather uncommon characteristic of presenting higher values both in fracture toughness and in tensile strength, this being very attractive for aeronautical applications. Typical fracture toughness of 2024-T3 and 7475-T76 from the literature [16-18] are 35,0 and 45,0 MPa.m^{1/2}, respectively. As can be seen in table 2, the measured fracture toughness of GLARE 1 3/2 0.3 is approximately 2.4 times greater than the toughness of its constituent alloy and more than 3 times greater than the toughness of 2024-T3.

The use of small SE(B) or C(T) specimens has some advantages if compared to M(T) specimens, that includes low cost of machining and testing specimens, light laboratorial facilities (200.0 mm wide M(T) specimens with $2a/W = 1/4$ hold approximately 130.0 kN before fracture, whereas the tested 25.0 mm SE(B) specimens fractured below 1.5 kN) and the possibility of performing tests inside small environmental chambers, furnaces or other experimental devices. The use of small specimens can also be useful at the material selection or material development stage, although the M(T) specimens are still necessary for material homologation. These advantages are amplified if the small specimen results can be used to predict the results of the larger M(T) tests.

The fracture toughness values presented in table 2, measured from 25.0 mm wide SE(B) specimens, were useful for residual strength calculations of 150.0 and 200.0 mm wide M(T) specimens. As can be seen in table 3, the predicted values showed good agreement to the experimental ones being always conservative ($\sigma_{res. theor.} \leq \sigma_{res. exp.}$). When W is up to 150.0 mm the results are in very close agreement, whereas for $W = 200.0$ mm specimens the predicted values are at least 12 % lower than the experimental ones. This difference was attributed to the capacity of wider specimens to resist more crack growth up to the instability point, giving then a higher residual strength [19-21]. It is important to see that the measured fracture toughness is maybe a material property whereas residual strength is a concept related to the combination of geometry and applied load (specimen size, crack size to width ratios, etc.). On the other hand, many components made of GLARE laminates can have complex geometries and/or they can be subjected to complex load situations so the fracture toughness could be useful to predict their residual strength, although M(T) specimens are still more representative of loaded fuselage panels.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The fracture toughness of GLARE 1 3/2 0.3 laminates obtained from 25.0 wide SE(B) specimens were useful to predict the residual strength of 150.0 and 200.0 wide M(T) specimens.
2. The predicted residual strengths were very close to the experimental values, particularly for widths up to 150.0 mm. For wider plates the predicted residual strength was more conservative. This behavior was associated to the higher crack growth capacity of wider M(T) specimens if compared to the small SE(B) specimens tested.

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